
Development of Products with Shiitake Mushroom: Chemical, Physical and Sensory Characterization

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Abstract Shiitake mushrooms are much appreciated and therefore their production has increased. However, an important quantity of by-products and residues, are also generated and which are considered as waste materials. In this way, the aim of this work was to develop new foods incorporating shiitake mushrooms that do not comply with standards for commercialization, thus providing additional sources of income for the farmers. For this, a filling with mushroom was produced for rissoles and pies, and the final products were analysed for their chemical composition, colour, texture and sensorial attributes. The results showed that the shiitake products presented an interesting chemical composition, rich in protein and minerals, and poor in salt. It was also observed that the frying operation induced more colour changes in the rissoles than the oven baking of the pies. The textural measurements indicated that the rissoles were much softer when compared to the pies, being also more cohesive and elastic. The sensory panel attributed high scores to both products (around 4.5, on a scale from 1 to 5), thus indicating that these may constitute an additional source of income to the farmers and at the same time reducing waste.

Keywords chemical composition, colour, compression test, puncture test, textural properties

Introduction

Shiitake mushrooms (*Lentinula edodes*) have been used in human diet for centuries and their potential as phytochemicals has also been established. Shiitake mushroom is the second most popular edible mushroom around the world, representing around 25% of the overall mushroom production [1–4].

Shiitake mushroom includes two different parts: the main body used for human consumption, which is the cap, and the stipe, which is normally discarded due to its hard texture. Still, the stipe has improved nutritional value and levels of bioactive compounds [5, 6]. Many studies have proved that shiitake mushrooms contain essential macro and micro nutrients as well as many bioactive compounds, including polysaccharides, antioxidants, dietary fibre, ergosterol, vitamins (B₁, B₂ and C), folates, niacin and dietary minerals [2, 6–8].

Sustainability has demonstrated to be absolutely critical for the development and continuation of mankind as residents of Planet Earth. The limited availability of resources from the soil and sea allied to the diminishing biodiversity in terms of fauna and flora, has led to the urgency in developing strategies within the framework of sustainability [9].

More than ever, the world faces the consequences of environmental problems that lead to global warming and climate change; water and air pollution; soil contamination, erosion and exhaustion, among others. Food waste also contributes for these environmental issues. Particularly, in the case of mushrooms, a significant amount of stipes (by-products) and also mushrooms that are too small or with the wrong shape (not commercially acceptable) are

considered as waste materials. However, this may bring possibilities and opportunities for farmers at local scale or even the food industry to increase economic profitability by adequate usage and processing of these mushroom by-products. Furthermore, farmers are faced frequently with the fact that some products do not comply with standards for selling either to the commercialization circuits or even to the industry, for example due to small size or irregular shape, although they are perfectly good in terms of taste, composition and nutritional value. Hence, studies focused on developing new added-value foods from these discarded by-products are valuable [10–13].

The objective of this work was to develop new valued foods incorporating shiitake mushroom, as a way to utilize the products that do not comply with standards for commercialization (in terms of size or shape), thus avoiding waste, and creating added value for farmers. Also, by providing additional food experiences, the farmers that have rural tourism houses might find alternative ways to increase the guests' satisfaction.

Material and Methods

Cultivation and harvest of the shiitake mushrooms

The shiitake mushrooms were obtained from a local farm named *Ementa Sustentável*, which produces shiitake mushrooms in wooden logs, inside greenhouses, and using exclusively organic farming techniques. The harvest is best when the mushroom's hat is open at 50% - 80% of its full development. The mushrooms are carefully collected so as not to damage the bark of the logs and at the same time to avoid leaving residues of the taken mushrooms. Following collection, a size classification occurs according to the categories: small, medium or large; and also according to their development status: open or closed. Then they are immediately stored in a refrigerator until they are sold or processed, never exceeding one week. Because open mushrooms are quite susceptible to a faster and more intense degradation, they are usually used for processing and transformation into alternative food products.

Preparation of the Pies and Rissoles

For the confection of the filling, 8 cloves of garlic were peeled and chopped, and then fried in a pan with 50 mL of olive oil. Then, 800 g of mushrooms were added and left to cook for a short while, until the mushrooms released all their water, followed by 300 g of chopped onions, 50 g of flour, 90 g of margarine and 50 mL of semi skimmed milk. The mixture was seasoned with parsley (8 g), salt (5 g), pepper (4 g) and nutmeg (1g) and left to cook for about 10 minutes.

For the preparation of the rissoles' dough were used 240 mL of water mixed with 15 g of margarine and 3 g of salt in a pan over medium heat, with constant stirring, until it was boiling. Then, 120 g of flour were added continuing stirring. As soon as the dough began to separate from the pan, the fire was turned off and the dough was removed from the pan with the help of a wooden spoon, placed to cool on a marble surface which was previously sprinkled with flour to avoid sticking. After cooling, the mass was kneaded until a smooth and elastic texture was obtained, and then with the aid of a roll the dough was spread until a thin layer was formed to form and fill the rissoles: small amounts of filling were placed on the dough which was then folded over the various filling portions, cutting then into the shape of half circles. These were passed on beaten egg and then on breadcrumbs, and finally they were fried in hot oil at 180 °C (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Rissoles in deep frying (left) and finalized (right)

For the pies dough, 150 g of flour and 30 g of margarine were weighed and kneaded together with 3 g of salt and warm water added at intervals until the dough lost its stickiness. After being well kneaded, a ball was formed with the dough, which was flipped out and covered with a cloth to stand for 1 hour. Finally, it was spread with a roll over a marble surface. Then, larger circles and smaller circles were cut for the bottom and top parts, respectively. The pies were shaped in metallic forms, with the filling put before covering with slices of dough, which were connected to the bottom dough and then brushed with egg yolk. Finally, they were baked for about 45 minutes, in an oven which had been preheated to 190 °C (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Pies under oven cooking (left) and finalized (right)

Chemical analyses

For the evaluation of the chemical composition, six units were selected from three lots of each product. The samples were grounded to guarantee uniformity and all determinations were made in triplicates following standard procedures of The Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International (AOAC, 200). The components evaluated were moisture, ash, fat, fibre, protein and salt (chlorine).

Evaluation of colour

Colour was measured using a colorimeter Konica Minolta CR-400, in the Cartesian Coordinates system: L*, a* and b* (CIELab colour space). Lightness is represented by L* and varies from 0 (black), to 100 (white), while the coordinates a* and b* can have negative or positive values: a* negative is green and a* positive is red; b* negative is blue and b* positive is yellow[14]. Colour measurements were made on 10Rissoles and 10 pies, three replicates on each unit.

Evaluation of texture

To analyse texture was used the texture profile analysis (TPA) obtained through a texturometer TA-XT2 (Stable Microsystems). The test consisted of two consecutive compression cycles separated by 5 seconds. The probe used was a flat 75 mm diameter (P/75), and the operating conditions were the following: 30 kg force load cell; pre-test, test and post-test rates equal to 0.5 mm/s; trigger force 0.1 N. The compression distance was 3 and 5 mm, respectively for the rissoles and pies. The textural properties: hardness, resilience, springiness, cohesiveness and chewiness were by means of the following equations (see Figure 3) [15]:

$$\text{Hardness (N)} = F_1 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Resilience (\%)} = (A_5/A_4) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Springiness (\%)} = (T_2/T_1) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Cohesiveness (\%)} = (A_2/A_1) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Chewiness (N)} = F_1 \times (T_2/T_1) \times (A_2/A_1) \quad (5)$$

Figure 3: Example of a texture profile analysis obtained for the rissoles

For all textural evaluations 10 units of each product were used, and one measurement was performed in each unit. The results were processed using Exponent software TEE from Stable Micro Systems.

Sensory analysis

Sensorial analysis consisted in tests for descriptive sensory profile, and was performed by a non-trained panel of 25 judges, who had some previous experience in sensory evaluations. The samples were presented to the panelists whole, over an odour-free white dish. Deionised water and unsalted crackers were provided for palate rising in-between the samples. The sensory attributes were evaluated for the dough and for the filling. For the dough were evaluated appearance (colour, uniformity), aroma (pleasantness), taste (salt, pleasantness), texture (hardness, crunchiness, thickness) and global appreciation. For the filling were evaluated appearance (colour, uniformity), aroma (pleasantness), taste (salt, curry, mushroom, pleasantness), texture (moist, creaminess, uniformity) and global appreciation. Finally, an overall assessment of the whole products was undertaken. All attributes were scored on a scale varying from 1 (the lowest intensity of the attribute) to 5 (the highest intensity).

Results and Discussion

Chemical composition

Table 1 shows the mean values and corresponding standard deviation for the chemical components analysed in the shiitake products. The moisture content was lower for the pies, 34.53%, when compared with the rissoles, being this mostly due to the dough, which is much more dehydrated in the case of the pies due to oven processing. The protein content was similar for both products, between 4 and 5%, which might be due to the shiitake mushroom, which has approximately 3% protein [16]. Mushrooms in general present low fat and cholesterol contents, being therefore considered as interesting sources of protein, with demonstrated biological effects, such as antitumor, antiviral, antimicrobial, antioxidative and immunomodulatory activities [17].

Table 1: Results of the chemical analyses made to the rissoles and pies filled with shiitake mushroom

Property (unit)	Rissoles	Pies
Moisture (%)	52.46±0.36	34.53±0.22
Ash (%)	2.15±0.19	1.78±0.03
Fat (%)	10.72±0.12	16.78±0.93
Fibre (%)	0.95±0.22	1.63±0.24
Protein (%)	4.87±0.19	4.43±0.13
Salt (%)	1.23±0.03	0.89±0.03

The presence of fat would be expected, having in mind that the dough for both products incorporates margarine. The value for the rissoles is lower, 10.72%, when compared to pies, 16.78%, because the amount of margarine incorporated into the pies dough was double of that in the rissoles' dough. The frying operation to which the rissoles were submitted did not seem to contribute much to the increase in the fat content, which means that the oil incorporation was low, due to a correct frying process and the high frying temperature. The kinetics of oil absorption is determined by multiple factors, including the oil quality, frying temperature, frying time, possible pre-treatments and finally the composition of the food product. In recent years there has been an interest in minimizing oil absorption during frying, by modification of the applied techniques as well as monitoring of frying temperature and oil degradation [18].

The fibre content was found low, between 0.95% and 1.63%, and the ash content varied from 1.78% to 2.15%, for the pies and rissoles, respectively, referring to minerals that remained after degradation of all organic matter and including dietary minerals. The salt content was also lower for the pies, 0.89%, as compared to the rissoles. Although people in general find more tasty products with more incorporated salt, this has been related with many health problems, particularly regarding heart health and kidney functions [19–21].

Colour

Figure 4 shows the results for the colour coordinates in the developed products, taken as individual samples and also calculated as averages of the 10 samples analysed, to investigate the degree of uniformity of the products. The results reveal that for all colour coordinates (L^* , a^* and b^*) there was some variation between the sample of the same product, being this variability more intense for the coordinate a^* , which refers to the intensity of the red colouration. This could be explained having in mind that both the frying oven baking operations induce important changes in colour, especially towards browning, which may not be totally uniform [22, 23].

The results in Figure 4 also indicate that the rissoles are darker, $L^* = 44.12$ against 54.64, and with a more intense brown coloration, resulting in higher values for redness, $a^* = 9.86$ against 2.40, and also yellowness, $b^* = 34.40$ against 27.14.

Figure 4: Colour coordinates for the rissoles and pies separated by sample and calculated as a whole

Figure 5: Textural properties of the products determined as average of TPAs performed on 10 samples

Sensorial characteristics

Figure 6 presents the sensorial characteristics of the filling and dough used in the rissoles and pies. The attribute least scored was salt, both in the dough and in the filling, indicating that the amount of salt added was low, as recommended for health purposes. Nevertheless, it was confirmed that the tasters do not quite appreciate the reduction in salt. The dough of the pies got higher scores for hardness, crunchiness and thickness, which is corroborated with the instrumental evaluations, made for texture. The dough of the rissoles received higher scores for uniformity, colour and aroma. The aroma score may be owing to the frying operations, since fried foods are much valued in general in terms of flavour. Regarding colour, the measurement made also indicated that the rissoles were darker and with more intense colours. Regarding the dough, it was most valued for taste, with scores of 4.31 and 4.27, respectively for rissoles and pies.

Since the filling used in both products was the same, it was expected that the results of the sensory evaluation would be similar, as verified in Figure 6. The attributes more valued in the filling were pleasantness of aroma, pleasantness of taste and creaminess, with values higher than 4, on a scale of up to 5 points.

The average score for overall assessment of the whole rissoles was 4.35 points and for the pies was just very slightly higher, 4.50 points (Figure 7). This indicates that both products were highly appreciated by the panellists, with average scores relatively close to the highest value of the scale considered for evaluation (from 1 to 5 points). The results also indicate that the dough and the filling were similarly scored, i.e., the panellist valued both parts equally.

Dough

Filling

Figure 6: Sensorial characteristics of the dough and filling of the rissoles and samosas

Figure 7: Global scores for the dough, filling and whole products

Conclusions

The present work showed that the chemical composition of the shiitake products developed was balanced, being particularly rich in protein and dietary minerals, and relatively poor in salt. Regarding the colour evaluations, it was observed that the rissoles were more influenced by processing, frying, when compared to the pies, oven baked. In terms of texture, the rissoles were much softer when compared to the pies, being also more cohesive and elastic. Sensory analysis allowed concluding that both, the dough and the filling, as well as the whole products were highly scored, thus indicating that they were appreciated by the panel lists. This is very important because it proved that using the low valued residues and by-products from the shiitake production can be used to produce added value foods, while also contributing for a reduction in waste management needs.

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